

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some new 2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole derivatives

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Amines and phenoxy derivatives of 1-(3'-chloro-2'-hydroxypropyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole were synthesized by reacting 1-(3'-chloro-2'-hydroxypropyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole with appropriate amines and phenols. These compounds were characterized by spectral and elemental analyses. All the compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Compounds containing 2-methyl-4(5)-nitroimidazole moiety have shown a variety of useful pharmacological actions and many of these have gained acceptance in clinical practice¹. In view of this, it appeared of interest to synthesize above derivatives bearing the 2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole moiety.

1-(3'-Chloro-2'-hydroxypropyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole was prepared by the method of Hoffer and Grunberg². This was then condensed with amines and phenols to give the amino and phenoxy derivatives **2a-f** and **3a-e** respectively.

Antimicrobial activity of the compounds was assayed by the cup plate agar diffusion method³ against bacteria *Escherichia coli* Sonawave MTCC 614, *Escherichia coli* MTCC 78, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 10536, *Staphylococcus aureus* NCIB6571, *Shigella dysenterica*, *Salmonella typhimurium* ATCC 19430, *Serratia marcescens*, *Alcaligenes faecalis*. Metronidazole was used as standard in all the test compounds studied. The test compounds were studied at concentration at 2, 4, 20, 40 and 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Compound **2c** was found to be the most active compound and it was found effective even at concentration 4 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ against all the bacterial strains used. Compound **2b** and **3d** had shown a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) at 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ against all the bacterial strains used. Compound **2a**, **2d**, **2e**, **2f**, **3a**, **3b** and **3c** were found to be ineffective at 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ against any of the bacterial strains used.

Experimental

All the m.ps were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃+TFA) on Bruker (300 MHz) and Hitachi 1200 (60 MHz) spectrometers using TMS as internal reference and mass

	R	R'	Ar
2a	H	iso-C ₃ H ₇	3a C ₆ H ₅
b	H	n-C ₄ H ₉	b o-ClC ₆ H ₄
c	n-C ₃ H ₇	n-C ₃ H ₇	c o-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄
d	H	C ₆ H ₅	d α -C ₁₀ H ₇
e	H	p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	e β -C ₁₀ H ₇
f	H	α -Naphthyl	

spectra on a Jeol JMSD-300 spectrometer. Compound **1** was prepared by the reported method².

1-(3'-Isopropylamino-2'-hydroxypropyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole (**2a**) :

To a solution of 1-(3'-chloro-2'-hydroxypropyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole (**1**) (1.04 g, 0.004 mol) in 10 ml of *n*-propanol was added 0.43 ml (0.004 mol) of *iso*-propylamine. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h. Removal of solvent under vacuum yielded a solid residue, which was taken in water. The aqueous solution was next treated with potassium carbonate, extracted with chloroform and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of chloroform yielded

a solid, which was crystallized from ethyl acetate-alcohol (0.8 g, 70.17%), m.p. 221° (Found : C, 49.58; H, 7.43; N, 23.14. $C_{10}H_{18}N_4O_3$ requires : C, 49.45; H, 7.22; N, 22.84%). IR (KBr) 3600 (O-H stretch), 3150 (N-H stretch of secondary amine), 1490 (N-O stretch of aromatic nitro group), 835 cm^{-1} (C-N stretch of aromatic nitro group); δ (TMS, $CDCl_3$) 7.2 (1H, s, N- CH_2 -CH (OH)), 3.45 (1H, t, CH_2 -NH-CH (CH_3)₂), 3.15 (2H, d, N- CH_2 CH (OH) CH_2), 2.45 (2H, m, NCH_2), 2.35 (1H, s, Me at C-2), 1.45 (6H, d, N- CH_2 CH (OH) CH_2 NH (CH_3)₂); m/z 171 (6.8), 224 (6.4), 227 (7.8), 243 (M+)⁺.

1-(3'-Anilino-2'-hydroxypropyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole (2d) :

To a solution of 1-(3'-chloro-2'-hydroxypropyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole (1) (1.04 g, 0.004 mol) in 10 ml of *n*-propanol was added 0.43 ml (0.004 mol) of *iso*-propylamine. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h. Removal of solvent under vacuum yielded a solid residue, which was taken in water. The aqueous solution was next treated with potassium carbonate, extracted with chloroform and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of chloroform yielded a solid, which was crystallized from ethyl acetate-alcohol (0.8 g, 70.17%), m.p. 129° (Found : C, 56.52; H, 6.25; N, 23.14. $C_{10}H_{18}N_4O_3$ requires : C, 56.48; H, 6.17; N, 22.84%). IR (KBr) 3600 (O-H stretch), 3150 (N-H stretch of secondary amine), 1490 (N-O stretch of aromatic nitro group), 835 cm^{-1} (C-N stretch of aromatic nitro group); δ (TMS, $CDCl_3$) 7.2 (1H, s, N- CH_2 -CH(O)), 3.45 (1H, t, CH_2 -NH-CH(CH_3)₂), 3.15 (2H, d, N- CH_2 CH (OH) CH_2), 2.45 (2H, m, NCH_2), 2.35 (1H, s, Me at C-2), 1.45 (6H, d, N- CH_2 CH(OH) CH_2 -NH(CH_3)₂).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (yields 55–89%) : **2b**, m.p. 185°; **c**, 204°; **d**, 129°; **e**, 204°; **f**, 182°.

1-(3'-Phenoxy-2'-hydroxypropyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole (3a) :

A solution of 1-(3'-chloro-2'-hydroxypropyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole (1) (0.83 g, 0.004 mol) in 10 ml of *n*-propanol was treated with phenol (0.47 g, 0.005 mol) and 0.75 g of anhydrous potassium carbonate. The reaction

mixture was next refluxed for 12 h. The solvent was then removed and the solid treated with chloroform (3 × 20 ml). The chloroform extract was first washed with 10% sodium hydroxide solution (2 × 10 ml) and then with water (2 × 10 ml). Further processing of chloroform extract yielded a residue, which was crystallized from ethanol. Yield (0.8 g, 76.4%), m.p. 212° (Found : C, 50.6; H, 5.19; N, 18.15. $C_{13}H_{16}N_4O_5$ requires : C, 50.34; H, 5.12; N, 18.18%); IR (KBr) 3333 (O-H stretch), 1500 (N-O stretch of aromatic nitro group), 1250 (asymmetric C-O-C stretch), 1045 (symmetric C-O-C stretch), 875 cm^{-1} (C-N stretch of aromatic nitro group); δ (TMS, $CDCl_3$) 7.9 (1H, s, H-5), 7.4–7.21 (5H, dd, m, C_6H_5), 4.1 (1H, dt, N- CH_2 -CHOH- CH_2 - OC_6H_5), 3.95 (2H, br, d, N- CH_2 CH(OH)- CH_2 - OC_6H_5 and CH_3 at 2); m/z (rel. int%) 277 (M)⁺ (0.8), 184 (12.6), 170 (40.1), 144 (67.5).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (yields 41–59%) : **3b**, m.p. 151°; **c**, 212°; **d**, 199°; **e**, 207°; **f**, 204°.

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